

ENHANCING IN-SITU ENVIRONMENTAL OBSERVATION TO SUPPORT DESERT DUST STORM EVENTS MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

Desert ecosystems are highly susceptible to global climate change, with rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and higher atmospheric CO₂ levels significantly impacting their structure and functioning. By combining a network of cost-effective sensing nodes with advanced remote and in-situ data fusion techniques, CiROCCO will be able to cover under-sampled deserts areas, as well as areas highly affected by Desert Dust Storms (DDS) and provide different services to four pilot areas (Egypt, Cyprus, Serbia and Spain). Focusing on the pilot of Cyprus, CiROCCO aims to analyze the interaction between the congested environment in the Municipality of Idalion and the impact of DDS on air quality and public health and eventually provide an air quality Early Warning System (EWS). The established EWS for DDS will be adopted by regulatory authorities in Cyprus and made accessible to the public through a website and mobile application. In conclusion, CiROCCO Project seeks to develop a comprehensive sensing system and EWS for DDS events, with valuable insights for similar areas in Cyprus and eastern Europe.

Keywords: in-situ measurements, remote sensing, Desert Dust Storms, Early Warning System, climate change

1. INTRODUCTION

The Eastern Mediterranean Region (EMR) is affected by three distinct Sand and Dust sources: the Middle East, Northern Africa, and the Sahel. Based on meteorological conditions, dust can travel thousands of kilometers depending on the prevailing winds and stability of the atmosphere, and eventually dust is brought to the surface by dry and wet deposition processes. In the EMR, dust emissions are found to be more favorable from Northern Africa and the Sahel during spring, while during autumn the EMR is affected more from the Middle East [1]. The meteorological conditions and the various emission sources in the region are determined primarily by land degradation and sand dunes in the deserts, accompanied by high winds, bare land cover and climate change.

According to climate change scenario, Mediterranean will suffer from greater aridity. Reduced monsoonal rainfall in the Sahel because of intense dry ground conditions, may exacerbate the DDS [2]. An alternative perspective links climate change with reduced Sand and Dust Storm (SDS) events and vegetation growth in the Sahara, as the West African Monsoon was extended to the north [3].

The phenomenon of DDS is strongly related *inter alia* with impacts on human health [4] and its monitoring and early prediction are critical. Recent advancements in technology and science enable SDS prediction and even SDS anticipation. However, due to the significant capital and operational costs and space constraints for building urban air pollution measurement stations, the existing air quality monitoring networks are sparse, even in highly developed and economically strong countries. Consequently, these networks cannot adequately capture spatio-temporal variations of air pollution originating from local emissions sources on top of transboundary pollution. This challenge hinders the ability of regulatory agencies to protect public health and control emissions that contribute to exposure.

The EU funded CiROCCO Project aims to bridge this gap by establishing an advanced sensing system for in-situ and remote sensing measurements, collected via a mixture of wireless communications, including also satellite, and local Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN). This sensing system will be tested in 4 Project pilots that correspond to under-sampled desert areas and ecosystems or areas affected by DDS events.

Pilot 2 of CiROCCO is implemented in the region of Cyprus, which is particularly prone to frequent and severe DDS events, which are characterised by high levels of particles at variable sizes (ranging from fine to coarse). As demonstrated in relevant studies, approximately 10 – 40% of air quality threshold exceedances of the island of Cyprus can be attributed to DDS events [1, 5]. Yet, a recent survey of stakeholders' perceptions and current practices revealed gaps in the implementation of predetermined action plans for public protection during DDS events, in addition to the absence of an adequate EWS [6].

The additional burden due to DDS on an already congested environment, such as the case of the Municipality of Idalion, where intense anthropogenic activity takes place, will be studied in CiROCCO.

2. METHODOLOGY

Overall, CiROCCO aims to establish an end-to-end sensing system composed of a distributed network of cost-effective sensing nodes coupled with state-of-the-art data fusion remote sensing and assimilation modelling techniques. The sensors network will enhance the current lack of ground observation in desert areas offering an operational and also easy to maintain and expand solution. The under-sampled desert areas and ecosystems covered with CiROCCO sensors are located in Egypt, Serbia, Spain and Cyprus.

More specifically, CiROCCO intends to collect data from sensing systems that will integrate low-cost stand-alone electronic sensing nodes, additional higher quality off-the-self sensing stations and medium-cost portable sunphotometers. Data from the different in-situ sensors will be collected through mobile monitoring campaigns and fused [7]. In-situ measurements will then be fused with remote sensing data and further calibrated. For the collection of data, a mix of wireless communications including satellite, and local WSN will be used.

The quality of the collected data will be validated in four different services that will be developed in CiROCCO: *Renewable Energy Systems (RES) Planning*, *Air quality Early Warning System (EWS) for human health*, *Land use and ecosystem management* and *Modelling of Greenhouse Gases (GHGs) and particles emissions*. Each service will be developed for a different Project pilot (in Egypt, Cyprus, Serbia and Spain, respectively) and all four services will jointly drive the sustainability and exploitation path of the overall system. CiROCCO concept is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. CiROCCO concept.

Focusing on the pilot of Cyprus, the performance of existing operational models of the Sand and Dust Storm Warning Advisory and Assessment System (SDS-WAS) with the inclusion of the additional data generated from the Pilot of Egypt (implemented in a remote location in the Sahara Desert) will be evaluated. Furthermore, the Pilot aims to study the interaction between the congested, due to anthropogenic factors, environment in the Municipality of Idalion and the burden posed by DDS events and their combined impact on air quality and public health. Additionally, the Project will establish an EWS for DDS events, utilizing improved forecasting capabilities, real-time data, and satellite tools. The system will be accessible to relevant regulatory authorities, to mitigate the impact on public health and the environment, as well as to the citizens of the area for their own protection and information.

In the Project and on the pilot site, new technologies will be developed and utilized. Ten (10) newly developed low-cost, stand-alone electronic sensing nodes will be deployed in the congested environment area and serve as data collection points. The sensors will measure *inter alia* air and soil temperature, wind speed, ozone, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ and the nodes will be designed to capture relevant meteorological and air quality parameters. In addition to the low-cost sensing nodes, one (1) higher quality system will be also deployed. This system is specifically designed to gather more precise and accurate data on meteorological conditions and air quality in congested environment areas. The Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance of the Republic of Cyprus and the University of Cyprus (UCY) both have Air Quality Monitoring Stations (AQMS) located in less than 20 kilometres. These AQMS will be utilised to evaluate the effectiveness of the low-cost systems that will be developed for the needs of the Project. Finally, the in-situ measurements of the pilot study will be transferred and made available to EWS. The architecture of the system is already available from a previous European program, the Life+ MEDEA project. The goal is to enhance and upgrade the system's capacity using the CIROCCO's results.

3. MAIN RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As CIROCCO Project is currently at its early stages, this Section summarises the anticipated results. First of all, CIROCCO solution will increase the currently limited number of existing data sources for meteorological models in the region. In addition, numerous meteorological and air quality data will be made available from CIROCCO system, further advancing the understanding of the underlying mechanisms that govern DDS and in particular the understanding of early DDS low altitude dynamics.

Combining satellite tools, products and ground measurements, this Project aims to enhance the forecasting capabilities of existing and under-development meteorological models, which, due to data sparsity, often provide outputs of poor accuracy or low resolution. Through its well-equipped and fully functional meteorological and air quality stations in a remote location in the Sahara Desert (Pilot 1), data will be made available to forecasters for Cyprus in real time.

The exploitation of higher quantity and quality datasets will be complemented by the existing knowledge and know-how accumulated in Cyprus in this domain and will result in the establishment of a robust and accurate EWS for DDS (valid for and exploitable in both the eastern Mediterranean and in broader areas). This EWS will be adopted by the relevant regulatory authorities in Cyprus, *i.e.*, the Municipality of Idalion and the Ministry of Labour, Welfare and Social Insurance of Cyprus and will be available to the general public through a website and also via a mobile application.

4. CONCLUSIONS

For Cyprus, as well as for other sites in the Eastern Mediterranean that are in close proximity to desert areas in the south (Sahara) and east (Middle-East), the lack of in-situ stations to record the meteorological conditions and other soil characteristics (size, mineralogy, etc.) at the source, which are

very important for DDS modelling, hinder early forecasting. CiROCCO Project will complement the currently limited number of existing data sources for meteorological models on Cyprus, enhancing by that way the forecasting capabilities of existing and under-development meteorological models and at the same time further advancing the understanding of early DDS low altitude dynamics.

The EWS that will be developed for the pilot of Cyprus will consider local needs and requirements and support public protection during DDS events, which is an issue of high priority in the area. Additionally, frequent and severe DDS events are not a local problem in Cyprus, as several Eastern Mediterranean countries are prone to them. The lessons learnt from the pilot of Cyprus can be easily transferred to similar areas in Cyprus and elsewhere in eastern Europe. By that way, CiROCCO Project can significantly contribute not only to the research made in this domain, but also to the development of relevant technological solutions to address this problem as encountered in other regions.

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REFERENCES

1. Achilleos, S., Mouzourides, P., Kalivitis, N., Katra I., Kloog, I., Kouis, P., Middleton, N., Mihalopoulos, N., Neophytou, M., Panayiotou, A., Papatheodorou, S., Savvides, C., Tymvios, F., Vasiliadou, E., Yiallourous, P. And Koutrakis, P. (2020). Spatio-temporal variability of desert dust storms in Eastern Mediterranean (Crete, Cyprus, Israel) between 2006 and 2017 using a uniform methodology, *Science of the Total Environment*, 714, 136693, doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136693
2. Solmon F, Mallet M, Elguindi N, Giorgi F, Zakey A, Konaré A (2008) Dust aerosol impact on regional precipitation over western Africa, mechanisms and sensitivity to absorption properties. *Geophys Res Lett* 35:L24705. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008GL035900>.
3. Pausata, FSR, Messori, G. and Zhang, Q., (2016) Impacts of dust reduction on the northward expansion of the African monsoon during the Green Sahara period. *Earth Planet Sci Lett* 434:298–307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2015.11.049>.
4. Neophytou, A. M., Yiallourous, P., Coull, B. A., Kleanthous, S., Pavlou, P., Pashiardis, S., Dockery, D. W., Koutrakis, P., & Laden, F. (2013). Particulate matter concentrations during desert dust outbreaks and daily mortality in Nicosia, Cyprus. *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology*, 23(3), 275–280. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jes.2013.10>.
5. Mouzourides, P., Kumar, P., Neophytou, MK-A, (2015) Assessment of long-term measurements of particulate matter and gaseous pollutants in South-East Mediterranean. *Atmos Environ* 107:148–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.02.031>.
6. Kinni, P., Kouis, P., Dimitriou, H., Yarza, S., Papatheodorou, S.I., Kampriani, E., Charalambous, M., Middleton, N., Novack, V., Galanakis, E. and Yiallourous, P.K., (2021). Health effects of desert dust storm events in the south-eastern Mediterranean: perceptions and practices of local stakeholders. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 27(11), pp.1092-1101.
7. Drainakis, G., Pantazopoulos, P., Katsaros, K. V., Sourlas, V. and Amditis, A. (2021). On the Distribution of ML Workloads to the Network Edge and Beyond, *IEEE INFOCOM 2021 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops*, pp. 1-6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/INFOCOMWKSHPS51825.2021.9484503>.